

Video Game Recommendation on Steam dataset using LightGCN

CS 276 Project Report

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I. INTRODUCTION

A. Recommender Systems

Recommender systems serve as backbone in modern digital platforms and guide users by recommending items of potential interest. These systems analyze user preferences and historical interactions with items to generate personalized recommendations. The primary objective is to forecast user interaction with items, encompassing actions such as clicks, ratings, purchases, and other forms of engagement. Recommendation techniques can be broadly categorized into three types: Collaborative Filtering, Content-based Filtering and Hybrid approaches. Collaborative filtering [4] techniques leverage user-item interactions to identify patterns and similarities among users and items, facilitating accurate predictions. Content-based methods utilize item attributes and features to recommend items based on their relevance to a user's preferences. Hybrid approaches combine collaborative filtering and content-based techniques to harness the strengths of both methodologies. With their ability to enhance user experience, increase engagement, and drive revenue, recommender systems play a vital role in today's digital landscape, serving diverse domains such as e-commerce, streaming platforms, and social media.

B. Collaborative Filtering

Collaborative filtering relies on the collective wisdom of users' past interactions to make personalized recommendations. By analyzing user-item interactions, collaborative filtering identifies patterns and similarities among users and items, enabling it to generate accurate predictions for items a user might like. For example, **User A** watched *Fast 5* and *Fast & Furious*, another **User B** also watched the same movies and additionally watched *Furious 7*. Algorithms using Collaborative Filtering will recommend *Furious 7* to **User A**. This is because **User A** and **User B** are “similar”. Fig. 1 illustrates how one can leverage Collaborative Filtering to recommend movies. Two primary approaches to collaborative filtering include user-based and item-based methods. User-based collaborative filtering compares the preferences of similar users to recommend items, while item-based collaborative filtering identifies similar items based on user interactions to suggest relevant items to a user.

Fig.1 An illustration of Collaborative Filtering [12]

This technique excels in capturing user preferences without relying on explicit item attributes, making it particularly effective in scenarios where item information is sparse or dynamic. The most prevalent approach in collaborative filtering involves learning latent features (a.k.a. embeddings), to represent users and items, enabling user-item interaction prediction based on these embedded vectors.

C. GCNs for Collaborative Filtering

Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) [9] have emerged as a promising approach for collaborative filtering (CF) [8], aiming to learn latent features or embeddings representing users and items by propagating them on the user-item bipartite graph. Traditional CF models, like matrix factorization [5], projected user IDs directly to embeddings, but later models, like SVD++ [6] and NAIS [7], incorporated user interaction history to improve embedding quality. Neural Graph Collaborative Filtering (NGCF) [4] builds on GCN [9] principles, leveraging the subgraph structure of users' one-hop neighbors to refine embeddings, achieving state-of-the-art CF performance. However, while NGCF's [4] adoption of GCN's [9] propagation rule seems promising, its heavy design inherited from GCN [9], including feature transformation and nonlinear activation, might not be optimal for CF tasks. This is due to the lack of rich attributes in user-item interaction graphs, making multiple layers of nonlinear feature transformation less beneficial and potentially detrimental to model training.

While GCNs [9] have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance for CF [3, 7], the underlying mechanisms driving their effectiveness remain elusive. Prior efforts to adapt GCNs [9] for recommendation tasks have lacked comprehensive analyses, overlooking critical insights into their operation. This study reviews LightGCN [2], a novel model designed to streamline GCN architecture

specifically for CF. By focusing solely on the essential component i.e. neighborhood aggregation, LightGCN [2] simplifies the GCN design [9], yielding a more concise and effective framework for recommendation. Through linear propagation of user and item embeddings on the interaction graph, LightGCN [2] achieves substantial performance improvements over existing models, including a relative enhancement over NGCF [4]. This simplified yet potent approach not only outperforms state-of-the-art GCN-based recommender models but also offers greater ease of implementation and training, supported by both analytical and empirical evidence.

II. STEAM DATASET

A. Dataset Description

The Steam dataset [1] utilized for training originates from the Steam video game distribution network, with a particular focus on the Australian Steam community, extracted by crawling users from the 'GameAus' community. Comprising **88,310** gamers and **10,978** purchased games, the dataset presents a comprehensive view of user-game interactions. Below is a table of the structure of an item in the dataset:

Variable	Description
user_id	Unique identifier of a user
user_url	Steam link to a user's profile
item_id	Unique identifier of a game
item_counts	Number of games owned by the user
item_name	Registered name of the item on Steam
playtime_forever	Number of minutes a user has played this game since ownership
playtime_2weeks	Number of minutes a user has played this game in the recent 2 weeks

Table 1: Description of the Steam dataset

B. Dataset Visualization

The "Playtime Forever" of the dataset is plotted, with a threshold of 2000 minutes of "Playtime Forever" used to define positive user-game interaction. It is observed that this threshold serves as a good basis for generating recommendations. Additionally, a significant proportion of users exhibit playtime durations falling within the range of 4 to 8, spanning from approximately 53 minutes to 3000 minutes.

Fig.2 Plot describing user density as a function of “Playtime Forever”

C. Dataset Preprocessing

The dataset preprocessing involved several steps to prepare the data for analysis. Created data structures: sets for unique user and game IDs, dictionaries for user and game data, and a list for user-game connections and playtime. Processing included extracting user info, adding user ID to unique IDs set, storing user URL in users dictionary. Subsequently, game information was extracted, with the game ID added to the set of unique game IDs, and the game name stored in the games dictionary. Finally, edge information was processed, recording connections between users and games, including playtime details. Overall, the dataset preprocessing ensured organization and structuring of the data for subsequent analysis and modeling tasks.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. LightGCN

Existing GCN [9] adaptations for recommendation tasks often incorporate feature transformation and nonlinear activation functions, which may be unnecessary for collaborative filtering. In response, LightGCN [2] simplifies the GCN architecture [9] by adopting a weighted sum aggregator and eliminating feature transformation and nonlinear activation. This approach, termed Light Graph Convolution (LGC), aggregates only connected neighbors and excludes self-connections, offering a more concise and effective framework for collaborative filtering.

Fig.3 LightGCN Model Architecture

In LightGCN [2], the graph convolution operation is defined as the weighted sum of neighbor embeddings, with symmetric normalization terms to prevent embedding scale increase. The layer combination operation in LightGCN amalgamates embeddings obtained at each layer to form the final representation of a user or item. This aggregation integrates embeddings from various layers, enhancing comprehensiveness and capturing graph convolution with self-connections. The final representation is determined by a weighted sum of embeddings, and the model prediction is the inner product of user and item final representations, serving as the ranking score for recommendation generation.

B. Model Training

LightGCN's [2] trainable parameters consist solely of the embeddings from the 0-th layer, equivalent to the model complexity of standard matrix factorization [5]. The model employs the Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR) loss, encouraging predicted values for observed entries to surpass their unobserved counterparts. This loss function incorporates L2 regularization controlled by λ to prevent overfitting. The model was trained for 40 epochs with a batch size of 1024 using Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001.

C. Project Implementation Flow

Fig.4 Project Implementation Flow

D. Evaluation Metrics

Recall@K metric was used for evaluating the model. Recall@K is an evaluation metric used in recommender systems to gauge the effectiveness of recommendation algorithms. It quantifies the

proportion of relevant items that are successfully recommended within the top-K items suggested to a user. A higher Recall@K value signifies better performance, indicating that a larger share of relevant items is included in the top-K recommendations.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In a comparative analysis, several node embedding models, namely Node2Vec [8], GCN [9], GraphSAGE [10], and GAT [11], were evaluated and compared to LightGCN [2] based on their Recall@10 performance for the recommendation task. The following table presents the Recall@10 performance of these models.

Model	Recall@10
Node2Vec [8]	0.21
GCN [9]	0.350
LightGCN [2]	0.337
GraphSage [10]	0.339
GAT [11]	0.342

Table 2: Performance Metrics for various GCN-based recommender models on Steam dataset

The following images show the visualizations of user and item embeddings in a 2D space.

Fig.5 user, item embeddings – Node2Vec [8]

Fig.6 user, item embeddings – GCN [9]

Fig.7 user, item embeddings – LightGCN [2]

Fig.8 user, item embeddings – GraphSage [10]

Fig.9 user, item embeddings – GAT [11]

<p>We recommend for user u76561197994136663: Green = Has the game, Red = Needs to buy the game</p> <p>g550 - Left 4 Dead 2 g243870 - Tom Clancy's Ghost Recon Phantoms - NA g377160 - Fallout 4 g238960 - Path of Exile g15190 - Brothers in Arms: Road to Hill 30 g9310 - Warhammer 40,000: Dawn of War – Winter Assault g17460 - Mass Effect g211820 - Starbound g443810 - This Is the Police g271590 - Grand Theft Auto V</p> <p>Node2Vec Recommendations</p>	<p>We recommend for user u76561197994136663: Green = Has the game, Red = Needs to buy the game</p> <p>g730 - Counter-Strike: Global Offensive g105600 - Terraria g4000 - Garry's Mod g72850 - The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim g218620 - PAYDAY 2 g550 - Left 4 Dead 2 g304930 - Unturned g377160 - Fallout 4 g8930 - Sid Meier's Civilization V g49520 - Borderlands 2</p> <p>GCN Recommendations</p>	<p>We recommend for user u76561197994136663: Green = Has the game, Red = Needs to buy the game</p> <p>g4000 - Garry's Mod g730 - Counter-Strike: Global Offensive g72850 - The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim g550 - Left 4 Dead 2 g218620 - PAYDAY 2 g49520 - Borderlands 2 g105600 - Terraria g271590 - Grand Theft Auto V g107410 - Arma 3 g304930 - Unturned</p> <p>LightGCN Recommendations</p>
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<p>We recommend for user u76561197994136663: Green = Has the game, Red = Needs to buy the game</p> <p>g730 - Counter-Strike: Global Offensive g105600 - Terraria g49520 - Borderlands 2 g252950 - Rocket League g550 - Left 4 Dead 2 g4000 - Garry's Mod g304930 - Unturned g211820 - Starbound g72850 - The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim g271590 - Grand Theft Auto V</p> <p>GraphSAGE Recommendations</p>	<p>We recommend for user u76561197994136663: Green = Has the game, Red = Needs to buy the game</p> <p>g105600 - Terraria g4000 - Garry's Mod g730 - Counter-Strike: Global Offensive g49520 - Borderlands 2 g377160 - Fallout 4 g252490 - Rust g550 - Left 4 Dead 2 g218230 - PlanetSide 2 g230410 - Warframe g72850 - The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim</p> <p>GAT Recommendations</p>	
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Fig.10 Example Recommendations Generated

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The performance of LightGCN [2] on Steam dataset [1] is subpar, potentially due to the sole consideration of "play time forever" with a threshold. Contrary to the notion that Collaborative Filtering can suffice without non-linearity and feature transformations, LightGCN's [2] limitation arises from its focus solely on interactions over the user-item bipartite graph. Incorporating user and item features could significantly enhance the model's latent representations, facilitating more efficient capture of user-item similarity. Therefore, the findings suggest that leveraging user and item features is crucial for improving recommendation performance, highlighting the importance of incorporating additional contextual information in collaborative filtering models.

While LightGCN [2] offers a straightforward architecture with trainable parameters limited to the embeddings of the 0-th layer, its reliance on a single layer may limit its expressiveness compared to more complex models. The absence of dropout mechanisms, commonly used in GCNs [9] and NGCF [3], could potentially lead to overfitting, although L2 regularization on the embedding layer helps mitigate this risk. Additionally, LightGCN's [2] fixed layer combination coefficients may not capture the diverse preferences and behaviors of users and items adequately. Future directions could explore personalized layer combination weights and adaptive-order smoothing to tailor the model to individual users and items, enhancing recommendation quality. Moreover, advanced negative sampling strategies and attention mechanisms could be investigated to further improve LightGCN's [2] training efficiency and recommendation performance, addressing its current limitations and paving the way for more sophisticated recommendation systems. LightGCN [2] can also be adapted to more diverse datasets targeting the recommendation task.

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